

INTERVIEW GUIDE

Impact of Sports Programs on Students with Intellectual Disabilities

GENERAL INFORMATION

Type	Semi-structured, open-ended
Duration	±30–50 minutes
Technique	In-depth Interview
Recording	Audio (with informed consent)
Location	School / community / home (as agreed)

NOTES FOR INTERVIEWER

- Use simple and empathetic language throughout the interview.
- Allow sufficient time for the respondent to think and respond.
- Use neutral probing: “Could you tell me more?”, “What do you mean by that?”, “How did you feel at that moment?”
- Avoid leading or suggestive questions.

PART I

INTERVIEW GUIDE FOR TEACHERS / COACHES

1 Opening

1. How long have you been involved in the sports program?
2. What is your primary role in the sports program?

2 Active Participation

Main Questions:

1. How would you describe students' level of participation in the sports program?
2. What factors influence their participation?
3. What strategies do you use to increase active involvement?

Probing:

- ▶ *Are there differences in participation across different types of disabilities?*
- ▶ *How do other students with disabilities respond when they see peers actively participating?*

3 Physical Fitness

Main Questions:

1. Have you observed improvements in students' physical capabilities?
2. How do you measure or observe these improvements?
3. What forms of training adaptation are provided?

Probing:

- ▶ *Are game rules modified to accommodate students?*
- ▶ *How are assistive tools or adaptations used?*

4

Psychosocial Well-Being

Main Questions:

1. Have you observed changes in participants' self-confidence?
2. How do participants interact socially with each other and with non-disabled peers?
3. Does this program support social inclusion?

Probing:

- ▶ *Has there been a reduction in stigma?*
- ▶ *How does the group dynamic function during training?*

5

Challenges & Implementation

Main Questions:

1. What are the main challenges in running this sports program?
2. Are facilities and resources adequate?
3. How is the program supported by the school, parents, and community?

6

Program Evaluation

Main Questions:

1. What are the main strengths of the sports program?
2. What aspects need further development?
3. Is the sports program sustainable? Why?

PART II

INTERVIEW GUIDE FOR PARENTS

1 Opening (Rapport Building)

1. Could you tell me a little about your child? (age, type of disability, daily activities)
2. How long has your child been participating in the sports program?

2 Active Participation

Main Questions:

1. How did your child first get involved in this sports program?
2. How regularly does your child attend the activities?
3. Have you noticed changes in your child's interest or motivation toward sports since joining the program?

Probing:

- ▶ *Does your child seem more enthusiastic than before?*
- ▶ *Does your child attend voluntarily, or do they need encouragement?*

3 Physical Fitness

Main Questions:

1. Have you noticed changes in your child's physical condition since joining the sports program?
2. What about their stamina, strength, or movement coordination?

Probing:

- ▶ *Is your child more physically active at home?*
- ▶ *Have there been changes in general health (e.g., getting sick less often)?*
- ▶ *Has there been an increase in independence in daily activities?*

4**Psychosocial Well-Being****Main Questions:**

1. Have you noticed changes in your child's self-confidence?
2. How are your child's social relationships with peers since joining the program?
3. Does your child appear happier or more self-assured?

Probing:

- ▶ *Is your child more willing to speak up?*
- ▶ *Has your child made new friends?*

5**Environment & Support****Main Questions:**

1. What support has the school or community provided for your child?
2. How has the coach/teacher supported your child?
3. Have there been any challenges during the program?

6**Reflection & Recommendations****Main Questions:**

1. In your view, what is the greatest benefit of this program?
2. What improvements are needed?
3. Would you recommend this program to other parents? Why?

PEDOMAN WAWANCARA

Dampak Program Olahraga terhadap Siswa Tunagrahita Berprestasi

INFORMASI UMUM

Jenis Wawancara	Semi-terstruktur, terbuka
Durasi	±30–50 menit
Teknik	In-depth Interview
Rekaman	Audio (dengan informed consent)
Lokasi	Sekolah / komunitas / rumah (sesuai kesepakatan)

CATATAN UNTUK PEWAWANCARA

- Gunakan bahasa yang sederhana dan empatik.
- Berikan waktu cukup bagi responden untuk berpikir dan merespons.
- Gunakan probing netral: “Bisa diceritakan lebih lanjut?”, “Apa maksudnya?”, “Bagaimana perasaan Anda saat itu?”
- Hindari pertanyaan yang bersifat sugestif atau mengarahkan.

BAGIAN II

PEDOMAN WAWANCARA GURU / PELATIH

1 Pembuka

1. Sudah berapa lama Bapak/Ibu terlibat dalam program olahraga ini?
2. Apa peran utama Bapak/Ibu dalam program olahraga?

2 Partisipasi Aktif

Pertanyaan Utama:

1. Bagaimana tingkat partisipasi siswa dengan disabilitas dalam program olahraga?
2. Faktor apa yang memengaruhi partisipasi mereka?
3. Bagaimana strategi yang digunakan untuk meningkatkan keterlibatan aktif?

Probing:

- ▶ *Apakah ada perbedaan partisipasi antar jenis disabilitas?*
- ▶ *Bagaimana respons siswa disabilitas lainnya melihat siswa yang aktif berolahraga?*

3 Kebugaran Fisik

Pertanyaan Utama:

1. Apakah terdapat peningkatan kemampuan fisik siswa?
2. Bagaimana cara Anda mengukur atau mengamati peningkatan tersebut?
3. Apa bentuk adaptasi latihan yang diberikan?

Probing:

- ▶ *Apakah ada modifikasi aturan permainan?*
- ▶ *Bagaimana penggunaan alat bantu/adaptasi?*

4

Kesejahteraan Psikososial

Pertanyaan Utama:

1. Apakah Anda melihat perubahan dalam kepercayaan diri peserta?
2. Bagaimana interaksi sosial antar peserta (kepada sesama disabilitas dan non-disabilitas)?
3. Apakah program ini mendukung inklusi sosial?

Probing:

- ▶ *Apakah terjadi pengurangan stigma?*
- ▶ *Bagaimana dinamika kelompok selama latihan?*

5

Tantangan & Implementasi

Pertanyaan Utama:

1. Apa tantangan utama dalam menjalankan program olahraga?
2. Apakah fasilitas dan sumber daya sudah memadai?
3. Bagaimana dukungan dari sekolah, orang tua, dan komunitas?

6

Evaluasi Program

Pertanyaan Utama:

1. Apa kekuatan utama program olahraga ini?
2. Apa yang perlu dikembangkan ke depan?
3. Apakah program olahraga ini berkelanjutan? Mengapa?

BAGIAN I

PEDOMAN WAWANCARA ORANG TUA

1 Pembuka (Rapport Building)

1. Bisa diceritakan sedikit tentang anak Bapak/Ibu? (usia, jenis disabilitas, aktivitas sehari-hari)
2. Sudah berapa lama anak mengikuti program olahraga?

2 Partisipasi Aktif

Pertanyaan Utama:

1. Bagaimana awalnya anak Bapak/Ibu mulai mengikuti program olahraga ini?
2. Seberapa rutin anak mengikuti kegiatan tersebut?
3. Apakah ada perubahan dalam minat atau motivasi anak terhadap olahraga sejak mengikuti program ini?

Probing:

- ▶ *Apakah anak lebih antusias dibanding sebelumnya?*
- ▶ *Apakah anak mengikuti kegiatan secara sukarela atau perlu dorongan?*

3 Kebugaran Fisik

Pertanyaan Utama:

1. Apakah Bapak/Ibu melihat perubahan pada kondisi fisik anak setelah mengikuti program olahraga?
2. Bagaimana dengan daya tahan tubuh, kekuatan, atau koordinasi gerakannya?

Probing:

- ▶ *Apakah anak lebih aktif di rumah?*
- ▶ *Apakah ada perubahan dalam kesehatan umum (misalnya lebih jarang sakit)?*
- ▶ *Apakah ada peningkatan kemandirian dalam aktivitas sehari-hari?*

4**Kesejahteraan Psikososial****Pertanyaan Utama:**

1. Apakah ada perubahan dalam rasa percaya diri anak?
2. Bagaimana hubungan sosial anak dengan teman sebaya setelah mengikuti program?
3. Apakah anak terlihat lebih bahagia atau lebih percaya diri?

Probing:

- ▶ *Apakah anak lebih berani berbicara?*
- ▶ *Apakah anak memiliki teman baru?*

5**Lingkungan & Dukungan****Pertanyaan Utama:**

1. Bagaimana dukungan dari sekolah atau komunitas terhadap anak Bapak/Ibu?
2. Bagaimana peran pelatih/guru dalam mendampingi anak?
3. Apakah ada kendala selama mengikuti program?

6**Refleksi & Rekomendasi****Pertanyaan Utama:**

1. Menurut Bapak/Ibu, apa manfaat terbesar dari program ini?
2. Apa yang perlu diperbaiki?
3. Apakah Bapak/Ibu merekomendasikan program ini kepada orang tua lain? Mengapa?